

The Impact of Corporate Social Marketing on Brand Equity Ingredients

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Thi Hanh Nguyen ⁽²⁾Thi Trang Nguyen
⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Thi Hanh Nguyen, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

Research shows that CSM is an important factor affecting CBBE (dairy products); more effective than advertising and delivery density. The study is evidence that consumer perceptions of CSM, CSM (perceptions) initiatives positively impact the 5 CBBE components (brand awareness, brand association, perceived quality, brand trust and brand loyalty). The results also show a positive impact relationship between CBBE components.

Keywords: Corporate social marketing, CSM, brand equity

1. Introduction

Green consumption has been introduced as a term in developed countries since the 1970s and has received great interest from marketing scholars (Ellen et al., 1991); mentioned in social marketing when environmental factors become a social issue (Peattie, 2010).

In recent decades, there have been many positive changes in customer perception and behavior. Consumer awareness encourages them to take responsibility for minimizing environmental damage by purchasing and using eco-healthy products (Paladino and Baggiere, 2008); and sustainable consumption exists when consumers realize “their need is not only for clean food and water, but also for maintaining a sustainable social and environmental system” (Martin and Schouten, 2012, p. sixty one).

Green consumption and / or sustainable consumption are seen as general trends for worldwide consumption (Young et al., 2010; Gordon et al., 2011; Lorek and Funchs, 2013; Nielsen, 2015; GmG, 2018, 2019; WBCSD, 2019), and in Vietnam are no exception (Nguyen Huu Thu, 2014; Hoang Thi Bao Thoa, 2016; Vo and Le, 2016; Nielsen, 2017; Nguyen et al, 2017; De Koning et al., 2015).

Consumers not only expect to use high quality, safe and environmentally friendly products, but also demand that they be provided by a reputable and socially responsible company (Vo and Le , 2016). Many studies of consumer responses to corporate responsibility initiatives around social issues (public health, education, social security and welfare, etc.) have shown that there are associations in consumer perception, forming beneficial business behaviors, such as increased buying intent (Brown and Dacin, 1997; Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001; Lee et al., 2011); customer loyalty (Barone et al., 2000; Bhattacharya and Sen, 2003; Lichtenstein et al, 2004); consumer satisfaction (Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006).

The Report on Commitment to Sustainable Global Development (Nielsen, 2015) and Sustainability in Vietnam (Nielsen, 2017) pointed out five factors that consumers consider when choosing to buy, in addition to favorable factors. With regard to brand health and trust, consumers pay high attention to products with a strong commitment from businesses (environmental friendliness and commitment to social values). The report also shows that 86% of Vietnamese consumers are willing to pay more to buy products / brands that are committed to positive environmental and social impacts. In particular, among the 6 most concerned issues, in general, Vietnamese consumers focus on three major issues: environmental sustainability, health and social security (Nielsen, 2017); In fact, consumers have been posing requirements for businesses not only to satisfy product-related requirements but also to pay attention to sustainable social benefits.

Consumers are increasingly inclined to become an environmentally and socially responsible citizen, so they also expect a commitment to sustainability - as a must from businesses to acquire. their trust, their support (Martin and Schouten, 2012; Neilsen, 2015, 2017). It can be said that sustainability is more and more present in

everyday life, consumers will increasingly recognize and reward companies that operate honestly and seek sustainable results (Martin and Schouten 2012 ; Emery, 2012).

The trend towards green and sustainable consumption places a requirement for marketing (business) to not only bring customer satisfaction and maximize profits (Levitt, 1960), but also to proactively implement responsibility to social issues (Lewin et al., 1995; Crane and Desmond, 2002; Hoeffler and Keller, 2002; Maignan and Ferrell, 2001, 2004); marketing must contribute to the formation of sustainable social behavior (Gordon et al., 2011; Emery, 2012), actively support sustainable economic development and achieving sustainability in the marketplace (Hunt, 2011; Martin and Schouten, 2012). In other words, enterprises must proactively apply / move towards Sustainable marketing such as corporate social marketing (Gordon et al., 2011; Martin and Schouten, 2012; Emery, 2012).

Corporate social marketing (CSM) is based on ethics, volunteering (both organizations / businesses and marketers) in the implementation of social responsibility (Kotler and Lee 2005a; Kotler, 2009); solving social issues and especially the aspect of environmental protection (Kotler, 2011). CSM is characterized by the impact of converting perceptions and behaviors of target audiences (communities, suppliers, customers or consumers, ...), thereby forming sustainable social behaviors. (Kotler et al., 2002; Kotler and Lee, 2005a, 2005b, 2008; Gordon et al., 2011; Lefebvre, 2011, 2012; Emery, 2012); create benefits for both society and business (Gordon et al., 2011; Inoue and Kent, 2012, 2014).

Enterprises implementing CSM initiatives / programs, in addition to contributing to solving social problems, also reap many achievements such as market growth potential, increased sales, or business impression (Bhattacharya et al, 2005; Bloom et al., 1997; Kotler and Lee, 2005b); increasing competitive advantage thanks to strong emotional as well as emotional connection with consumers (Meyer, 1999); increased corporate impression of consumers (Lichtenstein et al., 2004); building and increasing brand equity (Hoeffler and Keller, 2002); improving customer loyalty to businesses (Inoue and Kent, 2012, 2014).

In Vietnam, although the concept of corporate social marketing (CSM) is still quite new, CSM initiatives / programs and consumer reactions in recent years reflect this term. is an issue that receives a lot of attention and support from the community. Many CSM programs are not only meaningful in branding and sales but also bring many social values, contributing to changing perceptions and encouraging sustainable social behavior. For example, Vinamilk, with the program of the Milk Fund to Stand Up Vietnam, School Milk has contributed to improving the physical condition (donating more than 35 million glasses of milk) and creating the habit of drinking enough milk for the children; or the 1 Million Trees Fund for Vietnam program to promote environmental awareness and behavior. Dutch Lady Vietnam's Firefly Program aims to support and encourage the studious spirit of disadvantaged children. P / S brand with P / S program to protect Vietnamese smiles, or Lifebuoy with Vietnam Future program with over million clean hands and For a healthy Vietnam; thereby, in order to raise awareness, form good habits of children in personal hygiene, contribute to improving community health, ...

2. Literature review

2.1. Market orientation

Market orientation is an important argument of the marketing industry, often understood as the principle of marketing implementation, and has also been considered the philosophy since the marketing industry was formed (McCarthy, 1960). This argument holds that marketing is the main function of the company, for the primary purpose of any company is to bring customer satisfaction (Levitt, 1960); At the same time, it also emphasizes customer orientation and demand satisfaction, through integrating marketing activities with the goal of achieving higher financial performance for the company.

There are two main views of market orientation. The first is behavioral market orientation. Narver and Slater (1990) mentioned three components of the behavioral market orientation: customer orientation (full understanding of target buyers to be able to continuously create outstanding value for them); competitor orientation (understanding the weaknesses and strengths, capacities and long-term strategies of both current and potential competitors) and cross-functional coordination (coordinating the use of company resources in create outstanding value for target customers). The second point of view is cultural orientation. Kohli and Jaworski (1990) argue that the market orientation according to culture consists of three groups of activities: the company must be knowledgeable about the types of customers, grasp current and future customer needs; disseminating market information widely to departments - functions; and the company must promptly respond to the market.

Two perspectives on market orientation have a reciprocal effect. Combining the two views gives us a more complete picture of market direction: First and foremost, companies must be able to gather information to understand their target and potential customers. direction - customer focus); Second, they need to be knowledgeable about their competitors (orientation - focus on competitors); Third, companies must have the capacity to widely disseminate market information / data throughout the system - functional through formal and informal channels; In the end, the company must be quick to respond quickly, which will provide a strategic advantage.

Over time, the marketing concept emphasizes the role of the customer at the center of everything (Gunay, 2001); and marketers should not only see customers as regular consumers, but need to see them as individuals with access to information, intelligent, motivated, unique and rational (Crane and Desmond , 2002, Gordon et al., 2011; Emery, 2012); respect them as wholesome entities with mind, heart and spirit when in contact with them (Kotler et al., 2017).

Sustainable Marketing is when marketing is considered in and actively supporting the sustainable economic development, achieving sustainability in the market (Hunt, 2011; Martin and Schouten, 2012); contribute to the formation of sustainable social behavior that benefits both individuals and society (Gordon et al., 2011; Emery, 2012); and organizations can achieve sustainable marketing through green marketing (Green marketing), social marketing (Social marketing) and dialectical marketing (Critical marketing) (Gordon et al., 2011; Emery, 2012). Accordingly, Hult (2011) argues that "more market oriented" (Market Orientation Plus) is when an enterprise can achieve market sustainability according to the degree to which it is strategically adapting. to market needs (customer needs and all stakeholders' interests) through activities that demonstrate responsibility for economic, environmental and social issues.

2.2. Corporate social marketing (CSM)

From the point of view that a successful marketing strategy in selling products and services to consumers can also be used to promote ideas for social good, changes for a good society. than; The social marketing concept (SM) first proposed by Kotler and Zaltman (1971, p. 5) is defined as the 'design, implementation and control of marketing programs that are computed to work with. impact on the ability to accept ideas of social significance ". The meaningful appeal is expressed in "the main goal of the social marketing concept is to achieve organizational success by balancing the short-term needs of individuals and the long-term benefits of society" (Kotler 1972, page 54).

The topic of social marketing has attracted attention from many scholars and continues to be updated and improved. For example, Andreasen (1994, 1995) argues that social marketing is the application of marketing principles in the commercial sector in the analysis, planning, implementation and evaluation of programs designed to influence action. vi voluntary and involuntary of target subjects in order to improve the welfare of themselves and the whole society. Kotler and Andreasen (1996) describe social marketing as the connection from different application areas of marketing (for profit and non-profit) from the perspective of coordinating the marketer's goals with the team goals. the organization / business you are working with; Social marketing attempts to influence social behavior not only for marketers but also for the target audience and society in

general. Kotler et al (2002, p. 5) define social marketing as “the use of marketing principles and tools to influence the target audience in order to make them accept, give up, change their behavior and / or habit voluntarily for the benefit of themselves, the community and society at large”. Lefebvre (2011, p. 57) defines social marketing as "the systematic application of marketing concepts and techniques, to achieve specific behavioral objectives, for the benefit of the public or for the good of society" .

Social marketing has received great attention from academics, marketing researchers as well as other disciplines and has been used to evaluate the effectiveness of efforts (primarily from social organizations. associations, non-profit or non-governmental NGOs are designed and implemented to influence the perception and voluntary behavior of individuals in areas such as public health, inclusion in the community. contribute to community activities or participate in events / activities for a good cause), poverty reduction or social security and welfare, injury prevention, ... (Andreasen, 1994, 2002; Kotler et al, 2002, 2008; Stead et al., 2007; Truong and Hall, 2013). In Vietnam, there are two typical studies on applying social marketing in solving social problems in the field of public health and social security, including author Le Si Tri (2007) Bui Xuan Du (2010).

The concept of corporate social marketing (CSM - Corporate Societal / Social Marketing) is seen as an extension of the application of social marketing to the enterprise context (Drumwright and Murphy, 2001; Bloom et al., 1997, 2006; Hoeffler and Keller, 2002; Bhattacharya et al., 2005; Kotler et al., 2012). This process stems from the following two reasons: (i) enterprises assert their role as corporate citizenship, actively exercise responsibility for social issues (Lewin et al., 1995; Maignan and Ferrell, 2001; Hoeffler and Keller, 2002); (ii) consumers have been and continue to (concern about environmental pollution and other social issues), putting pressure on businesses to demonstrate ethics (business) and social responsibility. (Crane and Desmond, 2002; Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Inoue and Kent, 2014).

The consequence of the application of CSM is that the marketers (enterprises) not only execute marketing programs with the aim of maximizing profits but also targeting the social benefits; The introduction of CSM is also because the main purpose or characteristic of CSM initiatives or programs (CSM Initiatives / Programs) is to persuade consumers to perform the behaviors that society wants (Bloom et al., 1997 , 2006; Kotler and Lee, 2005a, b; Kotler et al., 2012; Inoue and Kent, 2014). It can be said that the emergence of CSM is due to the fact that businesses are expected to take on an increased responsibility, that is, not only for society but also changing social behavior (Kotler, 2011; Truong and Hall. , 2016).

Corporate social marketing (CSM) is defined as “the use of its own resources and / or its partners in the application of marketing initiatives with at least one category. economic darts related to social security and welfare ”(Drumwright and Murphy, 2001, p. 164); Accessed as "the use of corporate business resources to develop and / or carry out behavior change campaigns to improve public health, human safety, and protection. environment or community well-being ”(Kotler et al., 2012, p. 111).

The concept of CSM was born in the context that businesses are expected to take on more social responsibility (Kotler, 2011); CSM is meant as the application of marketing to better shape, more effectively and sustainably market, to increase the well-being and social well-being of people (Phils et al., 2008); and the CSM concept is also continually adapted as a planned approach to social innovation (Lefebvre, 2012).

CSM is based on ethics, volunteering (both organization / business and marketer) in implementing social responsibility (Kotler and Lee 2005a; Kotler, 2009; Kotler et al, 2012; Truong and Hall, 2013, 2016); solving social problems and emphasizing the aspect of environmental protection (Kotler, 2011). Therefore, CSM is seen as an important tool in the implementation of corporate social responsibility (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Kotler and Lee, 2005b; Bloom et al., 2006; Kotler et al., 2002, 2012; Inoue and Kent, 2014; Deshpande, 2016; Truong and Hall, 2016). Due to the effective impact of CSM on social behavior and the motivating effect on consumer behavior, CSM is considered to be an effective tool in achieving corporate marketing goals and objectives (Kotler and Lee 2005b; Kotler et al, 2012; Truong and Hall, 2016).

CSM can basically be described as social change marketing, that is, to promote positive change in social issues (health, education, environment, social welfare, ...), Forming the desired social behaviors towards a sustainable society (Gordon et al., 2011; Emery, 2012; Martin and Schouten, 2012); once social change is achieved, it will bring benefits not only to individuals, businesses but also to society as a whole (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Kotler and Lee, 2005a; Bloom et al., 2006; Gordon et al, 2011; Kotler et al, 2012; Truong, 2014; Truong and Hall, 2013, 2016).

The positive impact on personal behavior change distinguishes CSM from other types of corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities / programs performed by companies such as volunteering and sponsorship. Corporate philanthropy and sponsorship, Community volunteering, and socially meaningful marketing (CrM - Cause-related Marketing) - these are forms with the main purpose of increasing goodwill, contributing contribute effort and resources, through which the business is recognized as having a good social purpose - but not affecting or changing personal behavior (Bloom et al. 1997, 2006; Kotler and Lee 2005a; Truong and Hall, 2013, 2016).

CSM is distinguished by its ability to provide holistic benefits to society by producing tangible results on social problems, measurable through changes in personal behavior (Kotler and Lee, 2005b; Kotler et al., 2012); as well as changes in perception and attitudes are prerequisites for behavior change efforts (Gordon et al., 2011; Emery, 2012; Saunders et al., 2015). CSM emphasizes on changing perceptions and (social) behaviors that make it relevant to sustainable marketing, and at the same time encourages sustainable social behaviors (Emery, 2012, Martin and Schouten, 2012).

In general, CSM has five important characteristics, including: (i) the main purpose is to change the behavior or habits of the target audience (community, consumers, ...);

(ii) a voluntary or persuasive behavioral transformation (perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors), leading the target audience to voluntarily transform perceptions and behaviors for their own benefit in relation to each other. closely related to community and social interests;

(iii) flexibly apply the principles and techniques of traditional (commercial) marketing in the CSM operation management process; (iv) based on corporate performance commitments associated with stakeholders and corporate volunteering towards solving social problems or implementing corporate social responsibility. ; and (v) community groups (local) are often the main beneficiaries of CSM programs / initiatives, stemming from the fact that the application of social marketing is often sourced from organizations (government, social / non-profit organizations, ...), or implement corporate-sourced CSM and often collaborate with organizations (Gordon et al., 2011; Truong, 2014; Inoue and Kent, 2014; Truong and Hall , 2013, 2016).

2.3. Brand Equity (BE)

Brand Equity (BE) is considered as one of the most important concepts in both marketing theory and practice (Christodoulides and De Chernatony, 2010; Keller and Lehmann, 2006); key assets of marketing (Wood, 2000; Ambler, 2003); an asset capable of having a positive impact on the business itself and its customers (Aaker, 1996); is formed when a business decides to invest in a marketing program to develop a brand to reach existing and potential customers (Keller and Lehmann, 2003).

According to Barwise (1993), Feldwick (1996), and Riezebos (2003), around the mid-1980s, the concept of BE became popular as a financially oriented term that emerged when different firms were purchased and sold for an amount in excess of the company's net assets (which reflects the difference between a company's assets and liabilities). As noted by Feldwick (2002), the difference between the cost (when buying and selling of a company) and net assets is explained as brand equity; thus, the brand becomes something of a value for money.

In the late 1980s, brand equity was of high interest by marketing professionals to capture the value customers sought from brands, assessing the impact of brand building on perceptions and practices. customer behavior,

and the role of marketing in brands (Aaker, 1991; Riezebos, 2003). Next, a brand asset is proposed as a valuable intangible asset of the company, which should be carefully managed and continually invested in order to maximize its value (Aaker, 1991, 1996; Keller, 1993, 2008; Kapferer, 1997). The popularity of brand equity is due to its strategic and dominant role in achieving competitive advantage (Keller, 2008; Davcik et al., 2015).

Scholars want to understand how a brand is measured and what it means for a business, while practitioners want to understand how different ways will influence consumption decisions, thereby increasing growth. their brand equity (Crescitelli and Figueiredo, 2009; Baalbaki and Guzmán, 2017). Brand equity (BE), once properly and objectively measured with the right one, is effective in assessing the long-term impact of strategic management decisions (Simon and Sullivan, 1993 ; Kotler and Keller, 2012, 2016).

Several definitions of BE have been proposed, and most of them are based on Farquhar's (1989, p. 24) definition: "the added value of a product when a product is sponsored by the brand". BE as a group of elements that gain or lose associated with a brand (name and logo / logo) that increase or decrease the value of a product / service to a business or its customers. (Aaker, 1991, 1996); is the added value that a brand brings to a product (Srivastava and Shocker, 1991); Holbrook (1992), Simon and Sullivan (1993) define it as the financial effects of a brand; Keller (1993, 2003, 2008) considers it to be customers' knowledge of brands and this knowledge is influenced by marketing activities; Park and Srinivasan (1994) define it as an increase in a customer's preference for a brand. Kapferer (1997, p

25) defines BE by saying that 'a brand has an economic function, a brand's value is derived from its ability to create a unique, positive and prominent meaning in the minds of the majority of consumers. ".

BE or CBBE is a customer's different perception of a product with the same properties but with and without a brand (Edell, 1993; Yoo et al, 2002;

Yoo and Donthu, 2001); a set of attributes influencing customer buying decisions (Lemon et al., 2001); the added value of a product by consumer association with it with a brand name (Netemeyer et al., 2004); a set of characteristics that make up a unique brand in the market, allowing a company to charge higher prices and capture a larger market share than the unbranded product (Clow and Baack, 2005); etc ...

Although BE or CBBE is a widely accepted concept, its definition is difficult to grasp (Knowles, 2008). Conceptualizing it is such a complex problem that it causes the blind man to see an elephant syndrome, which are different perspectives that describe different aspects of this intricate and intangible asset (Ambler, 2003; Christodoulides and De Chernatony, 2010).

Despite the fact that BE or CBBE is one of the most popular concepts, has been discussed by academics and researchers for decades, there is a lack of agreement on its definition or management. (Keller, 1993, 2008; Yoo and Donthu, 2001; Vazquez et al., 2002; Davcik et al., 2015, Oliveira et al., 2015). This is due to the lack of consensus on background theory and viewpoints (Raggio and Leone, 2007; Anderson, 2007); and the diversity in the definition and the approach adopted to measure this concept comes from both financial and marketing aspects (Hsieh, 2004; Christodoulides and De Chernatony, 2010).

3. Research method

The main objective of the thesis is to explore and test the relationship of the impact of corporate social marketing (CSM) on the brand equity components from the perspective of consumers (CBBE), in the case of dairy products. in the Vietnamese market.

The mixed method is used. The research conceptual scales were developed based on existing literature and qualitative research (in-depth expert interviews and group discussions with consumers). Quantitative preliminary survey was conducted with 100 respondents to assess the preliminary scale. Formal quantification through direct interviews with 850 consumers and 780 available samples (observations). Data is analyzed using

a linear structure model (SEM) to examine the impact relationship of CSM, advertising, and delivery density on CBBE, and the causal relationship between these CBBE components. . Measurements of invariants and stability of the model were determined by a multiple-group confirmation factor analysis (CFA) method.

Research methodology used by the author in this topic is qualitative research method combined with quantitative research.

Methods of information collection (primary and secondary)

Use desk research to gather secondary information from a variety of reliable sources. Secondary data is collected, synthesized from academic articles, experimental studies, scientific works, ... related to the topic - research field; Research reports on the dairy industry in Vietnam by the Vietnam Dairy Association (VDA), Vietnam Consulting and Industry Company (VIRAC),

Institute of Policy and Agriculture and Rural Development (IPSARD), Stoxplus (business and financial information provider), EVBN (EU-Vietnam Business Network), Forbes Vietnam, Nielsen, EMI (Euromonitor International), Kanta WorldPanel, Deloitte, GmG, ... mainly in the period 2010 - 2019.

Overview of primary data collection methods applied in the topic

In-depth interviews: face-to-face interviews with experts who are scientists, marketing management consultants, and marketing / brand managers in the dairy industry. The purpose is to explore - determine the components of CBBE dairy products in the Vietnamese market; marketing mix activities are widely used by dairy businesses; assess CSM research concept content, step by step complete the content and scale of CSM perceived concept; synthesis, adjustment and addition of observed variables used of related research concepts.

Focus group discussion: conducted a discussion with two groups of subjects (adults, direct and frequent buyers of dairy products) to explore and clearly define the ingredients of CBBE dairy products in the Vietnamese market; consumer awareness of some marketing activities (CSM, advertising and distribution density) that have been used by dairy businesses in Vietnam; add and adjust the scale.

Survey research: (i) Preliminary stage: interviewing 100 respondents (in Ho Chi Minh City) who are surveyed through detailed questionnaires following a convenient sampling method to adjust and redefine scale structure to apply for official research; (ii) Official research phase: interviewed 850 respondents (500 consumers in HCMC and 350 in Hanoi) to test scales, models and related research hypotheses.

About tools for information processing, model analysis and testing

Survey questionnaires (preliminary and official) were carefully checked and failed answers were discarded. Next, encrypt and clean the data using SPSS software. Clean datasets are used to check reliability and scale value with analytical tools such as Cronbach's Alpha, EFA analysis, CFA analysis, and SEM structural model to test the model and theories.

Official research model from the point of view of consumer behavior based on perception, namely applying Ajzen's TPB model (1985, 1991, 2019). In which: intention - behavior (consumer loyalty to milk brand) is a result of groups of factors: (1) subjective standards (perception or knowledge of consumers about the brand These include AW and AS (Keller, 1993, 2008); in a social context of sustainable production, green consumption and / or sustainable consumption); (2) behavior oriented attitude (management and exercise; based on consumer perceptions and experiences towards dairy brands); and (3) behavioral control perception (marketing factors / activities that both directly affect behavioral intent - ie LO; and directly affect the remaining CBBE components - representing master standards. attitude and attitude). Variables affecting (regulating) the relationships that impact marketing activities on perceptions and intentions - consumer behavior towards brands are geography, gender, age, income, type product and brand origin.

4. Result

Table 1: Results of total variance explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	9,619	27,483	27,483	9,619	27,483	27,483	3,575	10,214	10,214
2	2,997	8,562	36,046	2,997	8,562	36,046	3,473	9,924	20,137
3	2,787	7,963	44,009	2,787	7,963	44,009	3,320	9,485	29,623
4	2,588	7,393	51,402	2,588	7,393	51,402	3,293	9,408	39,031
5	2,197	6,278	57,680	2,197	6,278	57,680	3,283	9,381	48,412
6	1,981	5,661	63,341	1,981	5,661	63,341	2,880	8,228	56,640
7	1,847	5,277	68,618	1,847	5,277	68,618	2,863	8,179	64,819
8	1,495	4,272	72,889	1,495	4,272	72,889	2,825	8,071	72,889
9	0,790	2,257	75,146						
10	0,699	1,998	77,145						
11	0,662	1,893	79,037						
12	0,647	1,847	80,885						
13	0,600	1,715	82,599						
14	0,541	1,545	84,144						
15	0,516	1,474	85,618						
16	0,499	1,425	87,043						
17	0,447	1,277	88,320						
18	0,412	1,177	89,498						
19	0,400	1,143	90,640						
20	0,369	1,054	91,694						
21	0,352	1,007	92,701						
22	0,291	0,832	93,533						
23	0,282	0,805	94,338						
24	0,267	0,762	95,100						
25	0,239	0,682	95,782						
26	0,215	0,614	96,396						
27	0,198	0,567	96,963						
28	0,184	0,527	97,490						
29	0,169	0,482	97,972						
30	0,161	0,459	98,431						
31	0,146	0,417	98,848						
32	0,136	0,389	99,236						
33	0,108	0,307	99,544						
34	0,089	0,254	99,798						
35	0,071	0,202	100,000						

Table 2: Results of rotation matrix of factors affecting CBBE

Biến quan sát	Nhân tố							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
AS1	0,798							
AS2	0,793							
AS5	0,784							
AS3	0,784							
AS7	0,758							
AW2		0,849						
AW3		0,800						
AW6		0,741						
AW1		0,711						
AW4		0,662						
BT5			0,802					
BT2			0,772					
BT3			0,753					
BT1			0,721					
BT4			0,680					
DI1				0,885				
DI4				0,854				
DI2				0,831				
DI3				0,795				
AD2					0,861			
AD6					0,841			
AD1					0,837			
AD4					0,836			
QL5						0,818		
QL6						0,788		
QL1						0,769		
QL4						0,667		
LO3							0,780	
LO1							0,752	
LO2							0,739	
LO4							0,711	
CSM5								0,838
CSM1								0,831
CSM3								0,831
CSM7								0,790

Chi-square=1174.560;df=532;CMIN/df=2.208;p=.000;
TLI=.948;CFI=.954;RMSEA=.039

Table 3. Results of hypothesis testing

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
AS2	<---	AS	1.000				
AS1	<---	AS	.822	.036	23.027	***	
AS7	<---	AS	.879	.037	23.622	***	
AS5	<---	AS	.930	.037	24.829	***	
AS3	<---	AS	.850	.039	21.964	***	
AW2	<---	AW	1.000				
AW3	<---	AW	1.012	.046	22.246	***	
AW1	<---	AW	.959	.045	21.239	***	
AW6	<---	AW	.824	.042	19.735	***	
AW4	<---	AW	.929	.045	20.872	***	
DI1	<---	DI	1.000				
DI4	<---	DI	1.400	.079	17.822	***	
DI3	<---	DI	1.213	.072	16.928	***	
DI2	<---	DI	1.160	.072	16.129	***	
AD1	<---	AD	1.000				
AD6	<---	AD	.974	.033	29.299	***	
AD4	<---	AD	.887	.033	26.706	***	
AD2	<---	AD	.780	.034	23.287	***	
CSM5	<---	CSM	1.000				
CSM1	<---	CSM	1.004	.036	28.006	***	
CSM3	<---	CSM	.926	.036	26.022	***	
CSM7	<---	CSM	.992	.037	26.676	***	
BT3	<---	BT	1.000				
BT5	<---	BT	1.020	.055	18.446	***	
BT2	<---	BT	.933	.051	18.181	***	
BT4	<---	BT	.938	.054	17.514	***	
BT1	<---	BT	.886	.052	16.942	***	
QL5	<---	QL	1.000				
QL4	<---	QL	1.070	.059	18.216	***	
QL1	<---	QL	1.033	.056	18.322	***	
QL6	<---	QL	1.000	.057	17.588	***	
LO3	<---	LO	1.000				
LO2	<---	LO	1.048	.052	20.172	***	
LO1	<---	LO	1.117	.055	20.285	***	
LO4	<---	LO	1.035	.053	19.454	***	

This result shows that consumers of dairy products today receive brand advertising in both intensity and content in a reciprocal relationship. Dairy businesses, in addition to refining content - advertising messages (advertising production), also need to invest a significant amount of budget in order to increase the visibility or coverage on channels and media. Information (advertising plan) is viewed to suit each target audience.

This result also supports previous empirical studies on evaluating the impact of advertising on CBBE components in different directions, or measuring perceived ad spend (eg, Yoo et al. , 2000; Ramos and Franco,

2004; Gil et al, 2007; Ebeid, 2014; Shariq, 2018; Le Dang Lang and Le Tan Buu, 2014a, 2014b, 2017); or experimental attitudes toward advertising (eg, Nguyen Dinh Tho and Nguyen Thi Mai Trang, 2011; Nguyen et al, 2011); or a combination of both directions (eg, Buil et al., 2013; Darabjerdi et al., 2016).

Other scales are also adjusted and supplemented to suit the market and research context, including brand awareness (5 observed variables), brand association (5 observed variables), perceived quality (4 variables observed), brand loyalty (4 variables), and perceived distribution density (4 variables). In addition, the overall brand equity scale (4 statement variables) is also adjusted to the research context.

The research results are the basis for the next studies to use to verify, compare and expand the scale system of CBBE components; about the marketing tools that affect these components, especially the conceptual scale "Perceived CSM". Overall, the research results contribute significantly not only to dairy enterprises and / or businesses interested in CBBE, marketing researchers in the Vietnamese market; but also has implications for international market researchers. In the field of behavioral psychology in general and marketing in particular, the measurement scales in the research need to be tested across many types of products, many different markets under many different approaches and methods. especially the concept of CSM (perceptions) because it is consistent with the trend of green consumption, sustainable consumption; sustainable marketing (Hunt, 2011; Martin and Schouten, 2012; Emery, 2012); and marketing 4.0 (Kotler et al., 2017) promote corporate social responsibility towards sustainable development.

5. Conclusion

In order to build and develop a brand, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of CBBE (Keller and Lehmann, 2006), most importantly, to understand the measurement of CBBE to effectively manage this CBBE (Kapferer, 2005, 2008); that is to understand the role of CBBE and its components, the sources of impact - that form CBBE, as well as how to measure them from a consumer perspective (Baker et al., 2005; Kartono and Rao, 2009b; Crescitelli and Figueiredo, 2009; Hoang Thi Phuong Thao et al, 2010; Nguyen Dinh Tho and Nguyen Thi Mai Trang, 2011). Therefore, the important implications of effective branding and development will refer to the measurement of the CBBE components and the source of the impact - the formation of CBBE, based on the results of the testing of the scales. , models and research hypotheses about CBBE and the relationship between CBBE components in the dairy industry in Vietnam; The relationships that positively affect marketing (CSM, distribution density and advertising) are on each of these CBBE components.

The findings of the thesis imply that marketing specialists, marketing managers at dairy companies, market research companies, marketing consultants - brands, ... can refer to and use the scales already. testing (Appendix 8) and: (1) applying the CBBE milk product component model (presented in Appendix 5) to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of branding (milk and other dairy products, or processed foods in general) by measuring the increase in the 5 components of CBBE; and / or (2) apply a theoretical model (presented in section 5.3, figure 5.1) to simultaneously evaluate and compare the impact of CSM, density of distribution and advertising on CBBE components, to intent - brand consumer behavior.

The theoretical model is also a suggestion for organizations or firms (interested in or within the dairy industry) for further verification and / or comparison with other specific marketing activities / tools (eg, press store icons, promotions, prices, product packaging, ...) impact these 5 CBBE components; extend the relationship of marketing activities or brand loyalty to (dependent variables or research concepts) brand preference, intention to buy / re-buy.

This model allows businesses to understand the performance of marketing in CBBE creation, apply specific marketing strategies / programs with the aim of influencing consumer behavior, increasing CBBE and business performance.

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